

NEOPHYTE INSTRUCTORS IN A LOCAL COLLEGE: A PHENOMENOLOGY

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Neophyte Instructors in a Local College: A Phenomenology

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Abstract

The study centered in describing the observable phenomena of experiences, coping mechanism, and personal insights of Neophyte instructors of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Moreover, the aim of the study was to determine the experiences, coping mechanism and insights that has been encountered by the Neophyte Instructors. The study utilized a qualitative type of research which was phenomenological in design, wherein there were 14 participants who are the Neophyte Instructors in a local college. It was found out that the Neophyte instructors experienced difficulty in Handled Multiple Subjects, Adjusted Classroom Management Approaches and Strategies, Had Established Communication and Rapport, and Considered Differentiated Instruction and Strategies. In terms of their coping mechanism, there were several themes that were extracted based on the responses of the informants such as Adjusting and Adapting Teaching Strategies, Seeking Assistance and Support from Colleagues, Reflecting and Self-Assessing for Improvement, Having Work-Life Balance, Participating on Professional Growth Opportunities, and Asking Students Feedback. Insights that were revealed from the responses were Widen and Explore More Professional Growth Opportunities, Need for More Professional and Technical Support, and Consider Giving Mentorship Programs.

Keywords: *neophyte instructors, experiences, coping mechanisms, insights, and phenomenological study*

Introduction

Neophyte teachers, also known as new teachers in the early stages of their teaching careers, play a vital role in the education system. They bring fresh perspectives and technological skills to schools, but their lack of experience can pose challenges. Proper training and support are essential to help them effectively teach and connect with students. Mentoring and professional. In education, one general issue relates to the retention and support of neophyte teachers. Despite their enthusiasm and potential, many new educators face high levels of stress and burnout due to the demanding nature of the profession. This can lead to a high turnover rate among neophyte teachers, impacting the stability and quality of education in schools. Addressing this issue requires comprehensive support systems, mentorship programs, and professional development opportunities to help new teachers navigate the challenges they encounter in their teaching journey (Hammond et al., 2017).

In the United States, particularly in New York, the first year of a teacher's career is crucial in determining their longevity in the education field. Neophyte teachers often face stress, inadequate support, and may feel unprepared to address behavioural and academic issues in their classrooms. Research shows that mentoring programs pairing new and experienced teachers are valuable for helping new educators navigate the challenges and uncertainties of their initial year of teaching. However, when these mentoring programs are not put into place due to budget limitations and a lack of administrative backing negative repercussions can arise (Dias et al., 2019).

In the Philippines particularly in Cagayan De Oro investigates the real-life experiences of new teachers at Lourdes College. Neophyte Instructors faced challenges during their first year of teaching on classroom management, teacher-parent's communication, and the teaching of the RVM Pedagogy. According to the research, through conducting workshops and training sessions it will help them overcome the challenges and strengthen the neophyte teacher's ability (Candilas, 2019).

Nevertheless, the teaching experiences and challenges faced by neophyte instructors directly impact the learning outcomes of students. Moreover, new teachers grappling with teaching difficulties may doubt the effectiveness of their methods in educating students. The implications extend beyond individual struggles, as this research could lay the groundwork for improving the teaching approaches of neophyte instructors within the immediate institution. Conducting seminars and related events based on the study findings could effectively address the teaching challenges faced by new educators. Considering these factors, the necessity to undertake this study is clear and pressing.

Further, several research have been undertaken in relation to this to fill in the gaps of this study. There are studies that contribute to the understanding of neophyte teachers' experiences, challenges, and instructional competence. The first study focuses on the effectiveness of mentoring programs for improving the teaching careers of neophyte teachers. Despite some universities and colleges in the Philippines implementing mentoring programs with varying approaches, content, and scope, the impact of these programs remains uncertain by Aguirre and Faller (2017) conducted a study titled, "Experiences of LNU Neophyte Teachers: Cues for a Viable Mentoring Program." This study focused on neophyte teachers at LNU), while the second study explores the instructional competence of newly hired school teachers, focusing on the competencies that demonstrate readiness and efficacy in required skills. (Asirit et al. 2022 conducted a phenomenological study titled "A Closer Look at Neophyte Teachers' Instructional Competence" in the International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management). This research, however, focuses on the experiences of neophyte instructors, including how they cope, and how they perceive themselves as neophyte instructors in a local college.

This research study aimed to disseminate the findings of my research study wherein the strategy to share information and support with new instructors at a local college is centred on a well-structured orientation program and continuous professional development. Initially, the plan includes workshops, seminars, and mentorship sessions that cover essential topics such as curriculum design, classroom management, technology integration, and college policies. Seasoned faculty members will mentor new instructors to offer ongoing assistance, ensuring they feel self-assured in their roles. Additionally, new instructors will have access to online teaching resources, best practices, and instructional videos for self-paced learning. To facilitate continuous growth, the plan encompasses regular feedback channels and collaborative opportunities. Monthly meetings will serve as a platform to tackle challenges, exchange teaching strategies, and share experiences. Instructors will be encouraged to participate in professional learning communities (PLCs), attend conferences, and workshops. Continuous feedback via surveys and one-on-one meetings will aid in customizing support to address specific needs. This proactive approach aims to foster a culture of improvement and excellence among new instructors, ultimately elevating educational standards at the college.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the neophyte instructors at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology to their experience of teaching. Its specific aim was to address the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the neophyte instructors in local college?
2. How do these neophyte instructors cope with the challenges they have experienced?
3. What are the insights that they can share to other neophyte instructors and to the academe in general?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research approach based on phenomenology to gain a better understanding of the in-depth exploration of the informants' experiences. This method is intended for use by qualitative researchers. It employs in-depth and focused studies of small groups of people to guide and support the construction of hypotheses. The results of qualitative research are described as descriptive rather than predictive (Neubauer, et al., 2019). Additionally, this method helped the researcher establish a connection with the participants. To enhance the trustworthiness and authenticity of the data, the researcher can seek additional explanations and verification from the participants.

This study embraced a qualitative research approach grounded in phenomenology, aiming to delve deeply into the experiences of the participants. By conducting in-depth and focused studies with small groups, the research focused on developing hypotheses and presenting findings descriptively rather than predictively. This approach fostered a strong connection between the researcher and participants, ensuring data credibility through feedback from the participants.

The design of this research was considered qualitative. One form of qualitative research method is phenomenology. According to Creswell (2013), phenomenology is a method for examining ideas or concepts that have shared significance for a small group of people (3-15). This method focuses on actual accounts of a certain phenomenon, challenging preconceived notions on human experiences, emotions, and reactions to a specific circumstance. It enables the researcher to delve into the perceptions, viewpoints, understandings, and emotions of those who have actually encountered or lived through the event or circumstance of interest (Hirsch, 2015). Therefore, phenomenology can be defined as a direct investigation and description of phenomena as consciously experienced by people living those experiences (Biemel & Spiegelberg, 2017).

In this study, phenomenology was chosen as the most suitable approach for this research endeavour. Given that the primary goal of the study is to gain insights into the experiences of the neophyte instructors participating in the research, a phenomenological investigation is considered crucial within this research context.

Participants

The key participants of that study were the neophyte instructors in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology at Kapalong, Davao del Norte. In that study, fourteen people were carefully chosen as research participants. Seven (7) of the fourteen participants took part in the IDI, and the remaining seven (7) participated in the focus group discussion (FGD), where they all convened in one location and discussed the responses to the questions I had given to them.

This determined number was chosen in accordance with Creswell's (2013) recommendation that a qualitative study should have between 3 to 15 participants. Data saturation in the data gathering process would be greatly enhanced by using this group of participants in a qualitative research study.

Purposive sampling was employed during participant selection to ensure that only individuals who could provide the required data were able to participate in my study. A set of inclusion criteria was heavily relied upon when using a purposeful sampling technique. This sampling strategy ensured the collection of real lived experiences because it was a non-probability type of sampling. This was ensured by the sampling approach, which used people who were actively engaged in or immersed in the topic under this study (Ellis,

2016).

The researcher adhered strictly to the aforementioned requirements during the recruitment procedure. (1) Each participant must be a novice instructor and have at least 1 year to 3 years of service in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology at Kapalong, Davao del Norte. (2) The participant must be a neophyte instructor at KCAST. (3) The participant needs to be an instructor teaching in all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Additionally, the researcher sought participants who had volunteered their time and expertise to support student activities or initiatives at the college, further demonstrating their commitment to the institution and its community.

While the researcher sought to include a diverse range of neophyte instructors, there were certain exclusion criteria. Individuals who did not meet the required experience level (1-3 years of service) or who were not currently teaching at KCAST were not included. Furthermore, instructors who had not taught across multiple programs within the college were also excluded. This focus on instructors with experience across the college's various programs ensured a breadth of perspectives and insights within the study.

Procedure

In qualitative research, there are numerous data collection techniques. Focus group discussions and in-depth interviews (IDIs) are the most popular research techniques (FGDs). On the other hand, qualitative data gathering techniques requires supplying data that might be used to comprehend the mechanisms underlying observed outcomes and evaluate shifts in people's opinions (Sutton, 2015).

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The researcher began by contacting the local college and obtaining permission to conduct interviews with neophyte instructors. Once permission was granted, the researcher identified a pool of eligible participants, focusing on instructors with 1-3 years of experience. The researcher then scheduled individual interviews with each participant, ensuring a comfortable and private setting for the conversation. During the interview, the researcher used a structured interview guide, asking open-ended questions about the participants' experiences as new instructors, including their challenges, successes, and perceptions of support received. The researcher carefully documented all responses, ensuring accuracy and confidentiality. Finally, the researcher thanked each participant for their time and contributions to the study.

Ethical Considerations

To guarantee the effectiveness of the conduct of this paper as well as to ensure the safety of the participants involved in this study, this study will strongly align with the highest ethical principles and this are the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is the researcher's obligation to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants. Self-sufficiency forgoes upholding participant and researcher friendships, trust, and confidence. The researcher verbally asks the identified respondents whether they are willing to share their experiences and be interviewed as my study participants before administering the interviews. As a result, the researcher plans out the interview schedule in advance. This is done to make sure the participant won't be a factor in them skipping, postponing, or cancelling crucial errands (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, the researcher created information consent forms for the subjects. The letter was sent to the selected participants for the study's progress. Before the conduct of the interview, the researcher asked permission to the participants to record their interview session. Also, the researcher upheld rapport and built friendship, trust, and confidence. Likewise, they were given free time to ask the researcher their questions at any point before, during, or after the interviews. More significantly, the researcher worked very hard to ensure that every aspect of the future IDI and FGD was kept secretly or highly confidential from the public. Also, the researcher informed the participants that they had the rights to be informed of the study result.

Beneficence necessitates dedication to limiting participant risks as opposed to maximizing their share of the rewards. The identity of the interviewee was kept a secret in order to safeguard each participant. No file of information was ignored or left unsecured since participants were always protected (Creswell, 2013). The researcher disguised the identities of the participants by using pseudonyms in order to prevent the sources of statements and responses from being known.

In this study, the researcher took steps to reduce participant risk. To guarantee the safety of the interviewer and the interviewees, the

researcher confirmed that all participants were in good conditions before performing the in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD).

Furthermore, to protect the safety of all participants, the researcher found a secure venue where the participants and researchers could conduct a face-to-face interview. Participants in the interview process were given the opportunity to relate their stories in a safe environment where they did not face rejection or judgment. There were no unattended or unsecured information files, and all participants were protected at all times.

Additionally, the researcher made sure that any sensitive topics were avoided in the interview guide questions because doing otherwise could have put the participants in a very vulnerable position. Neither the group discussion nor the interview with study participants caused any discomfort.

Justice necessitates a fair distribution of the risks and rewards based on the findings of the investigation. Therefore, it is important to recognize the contributions of each participant because they are crucial to the success of this study. In all of their endeavours, they must receive the proper credit (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

In this study, the researcher ensured that those who took part in the research were treated fairly. The participant's anonymity and confidentiality were safeguarded. The researcher avoided disclosing any personal bias and avoided exhibiting any interpretation that was based on their viewpoint while announcing the study's potential conclusions. Additionally, informants received enough advance notice that they were interviewed and were thoroughly informed about the interview's progress as it was being performed. Biases weren't tolerated, and the researcher ensured that the informants were at ease throughout the entire interview process. The researcher took care to respond to the informants in a way that was unbiased whenever they presented and expounded on their stance about a specific subject in order to display objectivity and professionalism.

Confidentiality towards the results and findings including the safety of all the data and the participants, coding system, and pseudonyms were used to hide the identity of the participants. All resources, including the videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and other materials that secured critical information from the participants, were to be destroyed after the data had been evaluated (Maree & Pieterse, 2007). Although the researcher assured them that their responses would be kept private, there were occasions during the interview when some of the participants were reluctant to answer the questions. The participant's voluntary and unforced disclosure of information was something the researcher always had to bear in mind.

In this study, the researcher ensured the confidentiality of the data collected by implementing measures to prevent data exposure and leakage, such as encrypting voice recordings, transcripts, and notes. The Data Privacy Act of 2012 was adhered to, with the researcher taking steps to encrypt and secure all acquired data, including personal information, to safeguard the participants' privacy. Furthermore, pseudonyms were used to maintain the anonymity and protect the identities of the study participants.

Consent was yet another crucial method to respect people when conducting research. This was done in order to inform all participants of the goals and purpose of the research study they would be taking part in. Additionally, this was a significant way to respect them during the investigation (Creswell, 2013).

In that study, participants were encouraged to make informed decisions and to participate voluntarily. The researcher made sure that everyone who participated in the study was enthusiastic about it. It was also vital to obtain consent from study participants to record their responses and share their experiences in order to collect data and information. The participants were also made aware of their rights, which included the right to ask questions during the interview, the ability to leave the interview without providing a reason, and the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. The researcher respected the participants' decision to leave the interview if they did so.

Results and Discussion

This section was subdivided into four sections: the initial section examined the participant data utilized for the acquisition of qualitative data; the second section encompassed the procedures involved in data analysis and the sequential stages involved in classifying emergent themes arising from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions; the third section addressed the responses to interview and focus group discussion queries associated with each research problem; and the fourth section encapsulated a synopsis of the collected responses.

Participants

The study participants consisted of neophyte instructors from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). Seven (7) participants in the focus group discussion and seven (7) participants in the in-depth interview made up the total number of participants in this study, which was shown in Table 1. All of the fourteen (14) participants were neophyte instructors.

In-depth Interview. In this research, a total of seven primary sources were identified, all of whom were Neophyte instructors at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. To ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants, each individual who participated in the comprehensive interview was assigned a pseudonym. The selection of these pseudonyms was based

on the participants' preferences and designated tag names, aligning with the principles of confidentiality. Assignment of pseudonym was made according to their unique physical characteristics, to their answers, and attitudes shown during the interview sessions. Like this, Aries was given the nickname to the informant because of the leadership qualities and determination, which can be associated with the confident and ambitious nature of Aries individuals. Taurus was the nickname given to the informant because it reflects his personality and that is reliable and practical in their approach to teaching, similar to the dependable and grounded nature of a Taurus, while Gemini was the nickname given to the participant since it reflects the way he answers the questions. Cancer was the nickname given to the participant as she demonstrate empathy and nurturing qualities of being a neophyte instructor, while Leo was the nickname given to the participant because it reflects how she directly gives her answers that strives to inspire and motivate his students. Virgo was the given nickname to the participant as it reflects her, while Libra was the nickname given to the participant since her answers was paying the attention to detail and analyses the student performance.

Focus Group. In the same manner, seven participants of the focus group discussion were also given pseudonyms. They were nicknamed as Adaptable was nicknamed to the participant who showcased great adaptability and flexibility in their responses to the given questions. Supportive was the chosen nickname for the participant who consistently provided encouragement and assistance to others during the discussion. Patient was the given nickname to the participant who demonstrated exceptional patience and composure throughout the interview. Resilient was the pseudonym assigned to the participant who displayed remarkable resilience and the ability to bounce back from challenging situations. Enthusiastic was the chosen nickname for the participant who showed high levels of enthusiasm and excitement during the entire session. Reflective was the given nickname to the participant who displayed a deep level of introspection and thoughtful analysis in their answers. Lastly, Versatile was the pseudonym assigned to the participant who showcased a wide range of skills and abilities in their responses. Both groups answered the same set of questions. The participants were selected according to their involvement and experiences of being a Neophyte Instructors. In which it was identified by the researcher and was verified by personal declaration of the participants.

The researcher employed a comprehensive approach to conducting in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, utilizing a combination of face-to-face interactions and social media platforms to ensure convenience for the participants. In order to accommodate the preferences of the participants, the researcher provided various options, including face-to-face interviews, messenger audio calls, and Google Meet. Among the participants involved in the in-depth interviews, five (5) individuals opted for online social media platforms as their preferred mode of communication, while two (2) participants expressed a preference for face-to-face interviews. The focus group discussion was conducted through a combination of messenger audio calls and face-to-face interactions, with two (2) participants choosing messenger audio calls and five (5) participants opting for face-to-face discussions. By incorporating both face-to-face and messenger audio call methods, the researcher acknowledged the significance of maintaining the study's validity and credibility. This approach allowed for a diverse range of participant preferences to be accommodated while ensuring the integrity of the research findings.

Table 1. Participants of the Study

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Aries	24	F	IDI-01
Taurus	24	M	IDI-02
Gemini	26	F	IDI-03
Cancer	23	F	IDI-04
Leo	24	M	IDI-05
Virgo	25	M	IDI-06
Libra	25	F	IDI-07
Total = 7			
<i>Focus Group Discussion (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Adaptable	27	M	FGD-01
Supportive	27	F	FGD-02
Patient	26	F	FGD-03
Resilient	28	M	FGD-04
Enthusiastic	26	F	FGD-05
Reflective	24	F	FGD-06
Versatile	25	F	FGD-07
Total = 7			
Grand Total = 14			

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, the messenger audio call and face-to-face recording were transcribed, translated, analyzed. The analysis began with the coding process. In order to provide meaning to data, the process of coding divides texts into smaller and smaller chunks. A description of the people's environment and groupings of topics for investigation are generated via the coding procedure. The study's overarching description was shaped by these topics. A table with the compiled data was provided. The information acquired was then sent to the data analyst for examination of patterns and trends.

The themes, sometimes called key themes, were provided in accordance with study questions to classify the data. The study's overarching topics were dissected at length for the sake of elucidation. The most important points of the respondents are shown in the table next to the overarching themes. The second step was the data analysis which we settled on as presented in Table 2. The data was organized thematically by presenting the themes in response to each study question. The co-ideas from the participants' replies were the polar opposites of the major topics in the table. The frequency of the answers was also tabulated, providing the data for the third column in the table that was used to determine which answers belonged to the "generic," "typical," and "variant" categories (Amparo, 2011).

Research Question No. 1: What are the lived experiences of the neophyte instructors in local college?

In order to address this research question, we conducted detailed interviews and group discussions with the participants. As a result, we asked several additional questions. The major themes and supporting statements for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: Handled Multiple Subjects, Adjusted Classroom Management Approaches and Strategies, Had Established Communication and Rapport, and Considered Differentiated Instruction and Strategies

Table 2. *The Experiences of Neophyte Instructors in Adapting Teaching Strategies*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Handled Multiple Subjects	<p>"I had a difficulty when it comes to the preparation, because imagine for a week, I will be preparing lessons on three to four different subjects, with just corresponding two or three sections. And that would be really challenging" (IDI01).</p> <p>"The most common challenges I encountered during my early teaching career is on how to handle a class and how to deliver the lessons effectively especially there are multiple subjects that I have handle"- (IDIO5).</p> <p>"One of the most challenging for me is that, I had to experiment with different approaches to effectively engage students and meet their learning objectives in various subjects that I teach"- (FGD03)</p> <p>"Balancing personal life and teaching responsibilities especially daily lessons for different subjects was overwhelming, especially in the early stages of my teaching career"- (FGD06).</p>
Adjusted Classroom Management Approaches and Strategies	<p>"One of the challenges I faced is adapting my teaching method in a classroom management. As I teach college students in history subjects, it can be difficult at times to capture their attention. There are instances when it feels like they are not listening"- (IDI02).</p> <p>"Adapting to different teaching methods and technologies also presented difficulties, as each class required a unique approach. A challenge that is establishing effective classroom management strategies to maintain a positive learning environment"- (IDI03).</p> <p>"The most common challenges I encountered during the early teaching careers is the classroom management because nowadays most of the neophyte teachers like us often learn through trial and error and how to establish effective classroom routines and manage student behaviour"- (IDI07).</p> <p>"One of the most common challenges I faced as a neophyte instructor was classroom management wherein It took time for me to learn how to maintain discipline and create a positive learning environment for my students"- (FGD01).</p> <p>"I had to experiment with different approaches to engage students and meet their learning objectives especially in a classroom management effectively"- (FGD03).</p>
Had Established Communication and Rapport	<p>"With colleagues, I actively engage in professional discussions, seek advice, and value their expertise to foster a supportive and collaborative environment. With students, I prioritize building trust, respect, and inclusivity by creating a welcoming classroom environment, actively listening to their needs, and offering academic and personal support. I promote fairness and equity, treating everyone with respect and ensuring equal opportunities for success"- (IDI06).</p> <p>"Building rapport with colleagues involves actively seeking guidance and support from experienced educators, attending faculty meetings, and participating in collaborative projects. With students, I aim to create a positive and inclusive learning environment by showing genuine interest in their progress, offering support, and providing timely feedback" – (IDI04).</p> <p>"I navigated relationships by seeking advice and support from experienced colleagues. Collaborating with them helped me learn from their expertise and build a strong network"- (FGD01).</p> <p>"Building rapport with colleagues and students required effort and time to earn trust and establish effective communication"- (FGD02).</p> <p>"I sought mentorship opportunities to navigate relationships. Having an experienced instructor guide me through challenges and provide feedback was invaluable in building relationships"- (FGD06).</p>
Considered Differentiated Instruction and Strategies	<p>"My instructional strategies and techniques as a neophyte instructor in local college. It would probably be focusing on being the center of knowledge. Because I do believe that as a teacher, I need to be the pioneer of delivering knowledge to my students. And with that, I should be the one who is giving off new concepts or introducing new concepts to the students. And basically to help them really understand the information or the topics I am presenting"- (IDI01).</p> <p>"My strategies in order for them to listen as well as learn, I will provide examples that they can relate to so that they can laugh and enjoy listening in my class"- (IDI02).</p> <p>"My instructional strategies and techniques revolve around creating an engaging and student-centered learning</p>

environment. I believe in employing a variety of teaching methods, such as lectures, group discussions, and hands-on activities, to accommodate different learning styles. I incorporate multimedia and technology tools to enhance learning experiences and foster active participation. I also emphasize the importance of formative assessments and provide timely feedback to guide students' progress"- (IDI03).

Handled Multiple Subjects

Neophyte instructors navigate the complexities of teaching multiple subjects, often encountering various hardships along the way. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions unveiled the challenges associated with how they've handled multiple subjects.

Aries (pseudonym) mentioned that the challenges they face when preparing lessons. Wherein he also mentioned about how demanding nature of their task, which involves creating lesson plans for multiple subjects within a tight one-week timeframe. In addition to that is the constraint of having only two or three class sections per subject to fit all the prepared lessons.

"I had a difficulty when it comes to the preparation, because imagine for a week, I will be preparing lessons on three to four different subjects, with just corresponding two or three sections. And that would be really challenging" (IDI01).

Furthermore, Leo (pseudonym) mentioned that teaching courses and managing a classroom effectively pose challenges. These include maintaining class discipline catering to individual student needs and promoting a learning environment. Additionally adapting lesson plans organizing sessions efficiently and ensuring instruction, across subjects add to the complexity of the teaching process.

"The most common challenges I encountered during my early teaching career is on how to handle a class and how to deliver the lessons effectively especially there are multiple subjects that I've handle"- (IDI05).

In addition, Resilient (pseudonym) mentioned that it is challenging as they had to tailor their approach, for each subject they taught and ensures to keep each,

Student engaged and interested they had to try methods and approaches. Besides maintaining student engagement ensures that all learning goals for each subject were met. This required them to experiment with, assess and adjust the effective teaching strategies for every subject and group of students.

"One of the most challenging for me is that, I had to experiment with different approaches to effectively engage students and meet their learning objectives in various subjects that I teach"- (FGD04)

Moreover, Versatile (pseudonym) mentioned that the difficulties they encountered balancing their personal obligations and their teaching duties. She clarifies that creating lessons for several subjects each day contributed to their demanding schedule, especially in the beginning of their teaching careers. They needed to figure out how to reconcile the demands of their career with their personal lives.

"Balancing personal life and teaching responsibilities especially daily lessons for different subjects was overwhelming, especially in the early stages of my teaching career"- (FGD06).

Adjusted Classroom Management Approaches and Strategies

Neophyte instructors set out on a life-changing road of education and self-improvement as they begin their teaching careers as they take the challenge head-on and apply modified classroom management strategies that promote an encouraging and diverse learning environment. Also, to provide their students with interesting and productive learning experiences by emphasizing the development of solid relationships, laying out clear standards, and utilizing cutting-edge teaching techniques.

Taurus (pseudonym) mentioned the constant drive to modify his methods in order to foster a more dynamic and interesting learning environment. He also states the understanding of the difficulties particular to instructing college students in history, where it can be especially difficult to hold their interest and attention.

"One of the challenges I faced is adapting my teaching method in a classroom management. As I teach college students in history subjects, it can be difficult at times to capture their attention. There are instances when it feels like they are not listening"- (IDI02).

Additionally, Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned the challenges she faced when it came to adapting her teaching methods and incorporating various technologies into her lessons. Wherein she recognize that each class is unique and demands a different approach, which added to the difficulty of finding the most effective teaching techniques for each situation.

"Adapting to different teaching methods and technologies also presented difficulties, as each class required a unique approach. A challenge that is establishing effective classroom management strategies to maintain a positive learning environment"- (IDI03).

Moreover, Libra (pseudonym) mentioned the challenges of upholding discipline, involving students, and fostering a supportive learning environment can be overwhelming. As inexperienced educators, she mentioned that always learning and modifying their methods to see what suits their students the best. The difficulty that emphasizes how crucial it is to create methods and approaches that provide a welcoming and inclusive learning environment in the classroom so that students can flourish both intellectually and personally.

"The most common challenges I encountered during the early teaching careers is the classroom management because nowadays most

of the neophyte teachers like us often learn through trial and error and how to establish effective classroom routines and manage student behavior”- (IDI07).

Furthermore, Adaptable (pseudonym) mentioned that It took time and experience for him to learn how to effectively maintain discipline and create a positive learning environment for his students. Managing a classroom involves various aspects, such as establishing clear expectations, implementing consistent routines, and addressing behavioural issues.

“One of the most common challenges I faced as a neophyte instructor was classroom management wherein It took time for me to learn how to maintain discipline and create a positive learning environment for my students”- (FGD01).

On the other hand, Patient (pseudonym) mentioned that she had to explore various techniques to actively involve students and support them in reaching their learning objectives, particularly in terms of effectively managing the classroom. Through experimentation with different strategies, she successfully identified the most impactful methods to engage students and help them achieve their educational goals.

“I had to experiment with different approaches to engage students and meet their learning objectives especially in a classroom management effectively”- (FGD03).

Had Established Communication and Rapport

Establishing communication and rapport as neophyte instructors in a local college can be a transformative experience, shaping the foundation of their teaching journey. As for neophyte instructors, navigating the complexities of effectively communicating their knowledge, values, and expectations while forging meaningful relationships with students is a crucial step towards creating an engaging and enriching educational experience. The interactions and connections they establish early on can set the tone for their teaching style, classroom management, and overall impact on the academic community, highlighting the significance of communication and rapport in their role as educators.

Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that he describes his approach to establishing communication and rapport with both colleagues and students. With colleagues, he actively engages in professional discussions, seeking advice and valuing their expertise. This demonstrates his commitment to fostering a supportive and collaborative environment, where he can learn from others and contribute to the collective growth of the academic community.

“With colleagues, I actively engage in professional discussions, seek advice, and value their expertise to foster a supportive and collaborative environment. With students...I promote fairness and equity, treating everyone with respect and ensuring equal opportunities for success”-(IDI06).

Moreover, Cancer (pseudonym) mentioned that they always ask for help and guidance from experienced teachers, participate in faculty meetings, and take part in partnership projects. In regards to students, they concern themselves with the creation of a friendly and welcoming environment that encourages the student to do their best and always lend a helping hand when the student needs it most and to ensure the student receives feedback in order to help them progress on the right path. In other words, it is about students taking the initiative to consult other students regarding their challenges or about teachers paying attention and being friendly and supportive to students in order to provide them with the best education possible.

“Building rapport with colleagues involves actively seeking guidance and support from experienced educators, attending faculty meetings, and participating in collaborative projects. With students, I aim to create a positive and inclusive learning environment by showing genuine interest in their progress, offering support, and providing timely feedback” – (IDI04).

Similarly to that, Adaptable (pseudonym) mentioned that they sought to regulate their interpersonal relationships by seeking help from other persons who were more knowledgeable in such matters. In this way, through interaction with these people, they were able to learn from the experience of professionals and augment their list of contacts as well. Well, as if they consulted those who were senior to them in their industry in terms of interaction and connection type.

“I navigated relationships by seeking advice and support from experienced colleagues. Collaborating with them helped me learn from their expertise and build a strong network”- (FGD01)

Furthermore, Supportive (pseudonym) mentioned emphasizing that in order to maintain relationships in both professional and social spheres with colleagues as well as students, one has to dedicate time and effort into it. They know that trust and communication are not something that can be easily built – it requires an individual’s commitment and efforts. In other words, they understand that developing rapport is a process that does not happen in a day but is a long-course process that requires the health commitment of both parties in the process of developing rapport.

“Building rapport with colleagues and students required effort and time to earn trust and establish effective communication”- (FGD02).

Additionally, Reflective (pseudonym) mentioned that she sought out mentorship with the aim of improving of their management of the relationship. All of them had a consistent instructor or a mentor to rely on and all these participants received advice which seemed extremely helpful in terms of developing more genuine relations with people. In other words, they accepted knowledge from someone

who had prior experience, and this helped them in the improvement of their relationships in the long run.

“I sought mentorship opportunities to navigate relationships. Having an experienced instructor guide me through challenges and provide feedback was invaluable in building relationships”- (FGD06).

Considered Differentiated Instruction and Strategies

Neophyte Educators, those, to teaching set out on a quest to grasp and apply methods that cater to the individual needs of their students. They face the task of establishing inclusive learning spaces that recognize and address each learner’s strengths, weaknesses and preferred learning approaches. As they explore the principles and application of teaching they manoeuvred through teaching approaches, evaluation methods and strategies, for managing classrooms.

Aries (pseudonym) mentioned that the approach of a novice instructor at a local college, who believes in positioning themselves as the central source of knowledge. She emphasizes the importance of being a pioneer in delivering information, suggesting that their role is to introduce new concepts and ensure that students grasp the material thoroughly. She sees her primary responsibility as guiding students through new topics and facilitating a deep understanding of the subject matter, indicating a more traditional, teacher-centred approach to education.

“My instructional strategies and techniques as a neophyte instructor in local college. It would probably be focusing on being the centre of knowledge...I need to be the pioneer of delivering knowledge to my students. And with that, I should be the one who is giving off new concepts or introducing new concepts to the students. And basically to help them really understand the information or the topics I am presenting”- (IDI01).

Moreover, Taurus (pseudonym) mentioned that to engage students and enhance learning, the instructor uses relatable, humorous examples to make lessons more interesting and enjoyable. This approach helps create a positive, interactive classroom atmosphere, making it easier for students to pay attention, understand, and remember the material.

“My strategies in order for them to listen as well as learn, I will provide examples that they can relate to so that they can laugh and enjoy listening in my class”- (IDI02).

Furthermore, Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned that teaching approach she uses focuses on creating an engaging and student-centred classroom. They use diverse methods, including lectures, group discussions, and hands-on activities, to cater to various learning styles. The instructor integrates multimedia and technology to enrich the learning experience and encourage active participation. Additionally, they prioritize formative assessments and timely feedback to support and monitor students' progress effectively.

“My instructional strategies and techniques revolve around creating an engaging and student-centred learning environment. I believe in employing a variety of teaching methods, such as lectures, group discussions, and hands-on activities, to accommodate different learning styles...I also emphasize the importance of formative assessments and provide timely feedback to guide students' progress”- (IDI03).

Research Question No. 2: How do these neophyte Instructors cope with the challenges they have experienced?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants, respectively, hence, several sub- questions were asked. The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: Adjusting and Adapting Teaching Strategies, Seeking Assistance and Support from Colleagues, Reflecting and Self-Assessing For Improvement, Having Work-Life Balance, Participating on Professional Growth Opportunities, and Asking Students Feedback.

Table 3. *The Coping Strategies of Neophyte Instructors in Adapting Teaching Strategies*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Adjusting and Adapting Teaching Strategies	<p>“I utilize differentiated instruction by adapting teaching strategies, materials, and assessments to accommodate individual student needs”- (IDI04).</p> <p>“Addressing any challenges or obstacles that arise during the learning process. For example, if I notice that certain concepts are difficult for students to grasp, I can modify my approach by breaking down the material into smaller, more manageable parts or providing additional examples and practice opportunities”- (IDI06)</p> <p>“I differentiated instruction by providing various pathways for students to demonstrate their understanding. This allowed each student to learn and progress at their own pace”-(FGD02).</p> <p>“When it comes to addressing diverse learning needs, I employ differentiated instruction. By adapting teaching methods, materials, and assessments, I ensure that every student can learn and succeed, regardless of their abilities or learning styles”-(FGD05).</p>
Seeking Assistance and Support from Colleagues	<p>“I only seek support when it is like I cannot have solutions of my own. For such cases, I would consult my program head or even the vice president for the academic affairs to give me insights on what to do, for example, that I have problems when it comes to with the grades of the students or their problems with the grades. I always consult my superior person with regard to that. And from there, I would also weigh all the ideas and suggestions and see to it that we could meet halfway in terms of decision making”- (IDI01).</p> <p>“I actively seek support and assistance to navigate through them. Firstly, I reach out to more experienced colleagues</p>

	<p>and mentors within the college for guidance and advice. Their insights and expertise provide valuable perspectives and help me find effective solutions..., I also make use of the resources provided by the college, such as instructional support services or teaching centers, which offer assistance tailored to the specific needs of instructors. By seeking support and assistance from various sources, I am able to address difficulties and continuously improve as an educator”-(IDI03).</p> <p>“I approached my department head or senior colleagues for advice and guidance. Their experience and expertise helped me navigate through challenging situations”-(FGD01).</p> <p>“When faced with difficulties, I reach out to experienced colleagues for guidance and support. They have been through similar challenges and provide valuable insights and advice”-(FGD02).</p> <p>“Seeking support from colleagues is crucial in addressing challenges. They provide a safe space to share concerns, offer suggestions, and collaborate on finding solutions to improve the teaching experience”-(FGD06).</p>
Reflecting and Self-Assessing For Improvement	<p>I practice self-reflection and embrace a growth mindset, viewing challenges as opportunities for learning and improvement. By adopting these coping strategies, I can effectively manage the challenges I face as a neophyte instructor in a local college”-(IDI03).</p> <p>“Taking time to assess my own emotions, thoughts, and reactions allows me to identify areas of improvement and develop resilience in the face of challenges”-(IDI04).</p> <p>“To manage the challenges I faced as a neophyte instructor...I set realistic expectations for myself and celebrated small successes along the way to maintain motivation and resilience”-(IDI06).</p> <p>“Engaging in self-care practices is essential for me. I make sure to set boundaries between work and personal life, engage in hobbies, exercise regularly, and practice mindfulness to reduce stress and maintain well-being” – (FGD04).</p> <p>“To cope with difficulties, I engage in reflective practices. Regularly reflecting on my teaching methods, seeking feedback from colleagues and students, and being open to continuous learning helps me adapt and grow as an instructor”-(FGD07).</p>
Having Work-Life Balance	<p>“In terms of self-care practices, there is a lot, actually. And maybe some of it is that I do traveling, drink wine, ice cream, especially when my body really asks for it... And I bet those are actually very effective because when there are stresses, I believe there's something you can do about it that can help you find the solution”-(IDI01).</p> <p>“Aside from school and work matters, I also involve myself in personal activities. For example, I engage in conversations or hang out with colleagues to build a healthy work relationship. Taking breaks from work-related matters can help reduce toxicity”-(IDI03)</p> <p>“I engage in activities such as regular exercise, practicing mindfulness or meditation, pursuing hobbies, and spending quality time with loved ones. Taking care of my physical and mental well-being helps me maintain a healthy work-life balance and approach challenges with a refreshed mindset”-(IDI05).</p> <p>“I do engage to reduce difficulties I have experienced is some sort of exercises such as yoga and self-meditation”-(IDI06).</p> <p>“Engaging in self-care practices is essential for me. I make sure to set boundaries between work and personal life, engage in hobbies, exercise regularly, and practice mindfulness to reduce stress and maintain well-being”-(FGD04).</p>
Participating on Professional Growth Opportunities	<p>“I actively participate in professional development workshops and conferences, where I can learn from experts in the field and connect with fellow educators facing similar challenges” – (IDI05).</p> <p>“I sought assistance through professional development workshops and training programs. These opportunities provided me with new skills and strategies to overcome teaching difficulties”-(FGD02).</p> <p>“I actively participated in faculty meetings and professional learning communities. These platforms allowed me to collaborate with colleagues, share concerns, and seek assistance collectively”-(FGD04).</p>
Asking Students Feedback	<p>“I embrace flexibility, encourage student engagement through various instructional methods, and continuously seek feedback to ensure that I am meeting the diverse learning needs of my students”-(IDI07)</p> <p>“I regularly communicated with students to understand their learning preferences and needs. This allowed me to adapt my teaching approaches and provide personalized support where necessary” – (FGD02).</p> <p>“I actively sought feedback from students themselves. Their input and perspectives helped me understand their learning needs better and find ways to improve my teaching methods”-(FGD05).</p> <p>“I encouraged student voice and choice in the learning process. By offering options for assignments and projects, students could showcase their understanding in ways that suited their abilities and interests”-(FGD07).</p>

Adjusting and Adapting Teaching Strategies

Neophyte Instructors often face the challenge of adjusting and adapting their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. They quickly learn that flexibility is key, as what works for one group may not be effective for another.

Initially, many may rely on traditional lectures, but soon find that incorporating a mix of group discussions, interactive activities, and multimedia resources better engages students.

Cancer (pseudonym) mentioned that she uses differentiated instruction, which is a teaching approach that involves modifying and tailoring the way lessons.

“I utilize differentiated instruction by adapting teaching strategies, materials, and assessments to accommodate individual student needs”-(IDI04).

Moreover, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that when challenges come up in the learning process, he tackle them by adjusting his teaching methods. If he sees that students are struggling with certain concepts, he change how he teach by simplifying the material into smaller, easier-to-understand chunks, and I offer more examples and extra practice to help them grasp the concepts better. This way, he can ensure that students have a better chance to understand and succeed.

“Addressing any challenges or obstacles that arise during the learning process. For example, if I notice that certain concepts are difficult for students to grasp, I can modify my approach by breaking down the material into smaller, more manageable parts or providing additional examples and practice opportunities”- (IDI06).

On the other hand, Supportive (pseudonym) mentioned that she tailored her teaching by offering different ways for students to show what they understand, which meant each student could learn and advance at a pace that suited them best.

“I differentiated instruction by providing various pathways for students to demonstrate their understanding. This allowed each student to learn and progress at their own pace”-(FGD02).

Similarly to that, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) mentioned that to meet the diverse learning needs of his students, he uses differentiated instruction. This involves changing his teaching methods, the materials he uses, and how he assesses students to ensure each one has the best chance to learn and succeed, regardless of their abilities or learning styles. By personalizing his approach, he can support each student in the way that works best for them.

“When it comes to addressing diverse learning needs, I employ differentiated instruction. By adapting teaching methods, materials, and assessments, I ensure that every student can learn and succeed, regardless of their abilities or learning styles”-(FGD05).

Seeking Assistance and Support from Colleagues

New instructors often find that seeking assistance and support from colleagues is invaluable to their development and success. For instance, a neophyte teacher might reach out to more experienced colleagues for advice on lesson planning, classroom management, or dealing with challenging student behavior. These seasoned educators can offer practical tips, share resources, and provide emotional support, which helps new teachers feel less isolated and more confident in their roles.

Aries (pseudonym) mentioned that she seeks support only when he feels she can't find solutions on her own. In such cases, she consults his program head or the vice president for academic affairs for insights, especially when dealing with issues related to student grades. She always discusses these matters with her superiors, then carefully considers their ideas and suggestions. She aims to reach a balanced decision that incorporates their input and addresses the problem effectively.

“I only seek support when it's like I cannot have solutions of my own. For such cases, I would consult my program head or even the vice president for the academic affairs to give me insights on what to do, for example, that I have problems when it comes to with the grades of the students or their problems with the grades...”- (IDI01).

In addition to that, Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned that he actively seeks support and assistance when faced with challenges. His first approach is to reach out to more experienced colleagues and mentors within the college for guidance and advice, as their insights and expertise provide valuable perspectives and help him find effective solutions. Additionally, he utilizes the resources offered by the college, such as instructional support services and teaching centres, which are tailored to meet the specific needs of instructors.

“I actively seek support and assistance to navigate through them. Firstly, I reach out to more experienced colleagues and mentors within the college for guidance and advice. Their insights and expertise provide valuable perspectives and help me find effective solutions”- (IDI03).

Moreover, Adaptable (pseudonym) mentioned that he would often approach his department head or senior colleagues for advice and guidance when dealing with challenges. Leveraging their experience and expertise, he successfully navigated through difficult situations with their valuable insights. Their support played a pivotal role in his professional growth and in overcoming obstacles effectively.

“I approached my department head or senior colleagues for advice and guidance. Their experience and expertise helped me navigate through challenging situations”-(FGD01).

Similarly, Supportive (pseudonym) mentioned when encountering difficulties, he turns to experienced colleagues for guidance and support. Knowing that they have faced similar challenges, he values their insights and advice, which have proven to be invaluable in navigating through tough situations.

“When faced with difficulties, I reach out to experienced colleagues for guidance and support. They have been through similar challenges and provide valuable insights and advice”-(FGD02).

Furthermore, Reflective (pseudonym) mentioned that seeking support from colleagues is vital when addressing challenges. Colleagues offer a safe environment where he can openly share concerns, receive helpful suggestions, and collaborate on finding solutions to enhance the teaching experience. This collaborative approach fosters a sense of teamwork and mutual support, ultimately leading to

more effective problem-solving and professional growth.

“Seeking support from colleagues is crucial in addressing challenges. They provide a safe space to share concerns, offer suggestions, and collaborate on finding solutions to improve the teaching experience”-(FGD06).

Reflecting and Self-Assessing For Improvement

Neophyte instructors benefit greatly from reflecting on their teaching experiences and engaging in self-assessment for improvement. By looking back on their lessons, interactions with students, and teaching strategies, they can identify strengths, areas for growth, and set realistic goals. This process allows them to make adjustments in their instructional methods, classroom management techniques, and overall approach to teaching, leading to continuous professional development and better student outcomes.

Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned that he practices self-reflection and embraces a growth mindset, viewing challenges as opportunities for learning and improvement. By adopting these coping strategies, he effectively manages the challenges he faces as a neophyte instructor in a local college. This approach allows him to navigate difficulties with a positive outlook, using them as chances to enhance his teaching skills and grow professionally.

“I practice self-reflection and embrace a growth mindset, viewing challenges as opportunities for learning and improvement. By adopting these coping strategies, I can effectively manage the challenges I face as a neophyte instructor in a local college”- (IDI03).

Similarly to that, Cancer (pseudonym) mentioned that He values taking the time to assess his own emotions, thoughts, and reactions as it helps him pinpoint areas where he can improve and build resilience when facing challenges. This practice enables him to gain a better understanding of himself and his responses, ultimately leading to personal growth and the ability to navigate difficulties with more confidence.

“Taking time to assess my own emotions, thoughts, and reactions allows me to identify areas of improvement and develop resilience in the face of challenges”-(IDI04).

Moreover, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that in managing the challenges he faced as a new instructor, he found it helpful to set realistic expectations for himself. By doing so, he was able to acknowledge and celebrate small successes along the way, which kept him motivated and resilient in overcoming obstacles. This approach allowed him to maintain a positive outlook and continue growing and learning in his role as a neophyte instructor.

“To manage the challenges I faced as a neophyte instructor...I set realistic expectations for myself and celebrated small successes along the way to maintain motivation and resilience”- (IDI06).

In addition, Resilient (pseudonym) mentioned that he prioritizes self-care as a crucial aspect of his life. Setting boundaries between work and personal time, pursuing hobbies, staying physically active, and practicing mindfulness are key components of his self-care routine. These practices help him manage stress effectively and ensure his overall well-being is maintained.

“Engaging in self-care practices is essential for me. I make sure to set boundaries between work and personal life, engage in hobbies, exercise regularly, and practice mindfulness to reduce stress and maintain well-being” – (FGD04).

Furthermore, Versatile (pseudonym) mentioned that he copes with difficulties by engaging in reflective practices. This includes regularly reflecting on his teaching methods, actively seeking feedback from colleagues and students, and remaining open to continuous learning. These practices enable him to adapt and grow as an instructor, fostering a positive and evolving approach to his role in education.

“To cope with difficulties, I engage in reflective practices. Regularly reflecting on my teaching methods, seeking feedback from colleagues and students, and being open to continuous learning helps me adapt and grow as an instructor”- (FGD07).

Having Work-Life Balance

Neophyte instructors often struggle to achieve work-life balance as they navigate the demands of their new teaching roles. Balancing lesson planning, grading, and classroom management with personal time for relaxation, hobbies, and family can be challenging. Many find themselves working long hours, sacrificing personal time to meet job expectations. This can lead to feelings of burnout, stress, and reduced job satisfaction.

Aries (pseudonym) mentioned that when it comes to self-care, she has several practices she finds helpful. She enjoys traveling, indulging in wine and ice cream, especially when her body signals a need for it. She believes these activities are effective in managing stress and finding solutions when faced with challenges.

“In terms of self-care practices, there's a lot, actually. And maybe some of it is that I do traveling, drink wine, ice cream, especially when my body really asks for it... And I bet those are actually very effective because when there are stresses, I believe there's something you can do about it that can help you find the solution”- (IDI01).

Similarly, Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned that aside from her school and work responsibilities, she also makes time for personal

activities. For instance, she enjoys having conversations or spending time with colleagues outside of work to foster healthy relationships. She believes that taking breaks from work-related topics can contribute to reducing any toxicity in the work environment, promoting a more positive and supportive atmosphere overall.

"Aside from school and work matters, I also involve myself in personal activities. For example, I engage in conversations or hang out with colleagues to build a healthy work relationship. Taking breaks from work-related matters can help reduce toxicity"- (IDI03).

On the other hand, Leo (pseudonym) mentioned that she prioritizes activities like regular exercise, mindfulness or meditation practices, pursuing hobbies, and spending quality time with loved ones to take care of her physical and mental well-being. This commitment helps her maintain a healthy work-life balance and approach challenges with a renewed and refreshed mindset. By investing time in self-care and engaging in activities that bring her joy and relaxation, she ensures that she can handle professional responsibilities and personal life with resilience and positivity.

"I engage in activities such as regular exercise, practicing mindfulness or meditation, pursuing hobbies, and spending quality time with loved ones. Taking care of my physical and mental well-being helps me maintain a healthy work-life balance and approach challenges with a refreshed mindset"- (IDI05).

Moreover, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that she engages in activities like yoga and self-meditation to alleviate the difficulties she encounters. These exercises help her reduce stress, improve focus, and maintain a sense of balance in her life. By practicing yoga and self-meditation, she finds ways to cope with challenges more effectively and enhance her overall well-being, allowing her to approach difficulties with a clearer mind and a more positive outlook.

"I do engage to reduce difficulties I have experienced is some sort of exercises such as yoga and self-meditation"- (IDI06).

Furthermore, Resilient (pseudonym) mentioned that he emphasizes the importance of self-care practices in his life, ensuring a healthy balance between work and personal well-being. By establishing clear boundaries, engaging in hobbies, regular exercise, and practicing mindfulness, he effectively manages stress levels and maintains overall well-being. This commitment to self-care allows him to recharge, stay focused, and approach both work and personal life with a positive mindset.

"Engaging in self-care practices is essential for me. I make sure to set boundaries between work and personal life, engage in hobbies, exercise regularly, and practice mindfulness to reduce stress and maintain well-being"- (FGD04).

Participating on Professional Growth Opportunities

The neophyte instructors at the local college are actively involved in participating in professional growth opportunities. They eagerly attend workshops, seminars, and training sessions to enhance their teaching skills and stay updated with the latest trends in education. These experiences not only provide them with valuable knowledge and resources but also offer networking opportunities with fellow educators and experts in their field. Through these professional growth activities, the neophyte instructors are able to gain confidence, improve their teaching methods, and contribute effectively to the academic community, ultimately benefiting both themselves and their students.

Leo (pseudonym) mentioned that he engages in professional development workshops and conferences, actively seeking opportunities to learn from industry experts and connect with other educators who are tackling similar challenges. By participating in these events, he gains valuable insights, stays updated on best practices, and builds a network of colleagues for ongoing support and collaboration. This proactive approach to professional development allows him to continuously improve his skills and stay informed about developments in the field of education.

"I actively participate in professional development workshops and conferences, where I can learn from experts in the field and connect with fellow educators facing similar challenges"- (IDI05).

Similarly, Supportive (pseudonym) mentioned that he sought help through professional development workshops and training programs, using these opportunities to gain new skills and strategies to address teaching challenges. By participating in such workshops and training sessions, he aimed to enhance his teaching abilities and find effective solutions to overcome obstacles encountered in the classroom. This proactive approach toward professional development reflects his commitment to continuous learning and improvement in his teaching practice.

"I sought assistance through professional development workshops and training programs. These opportunities provided me with new skills and strategies to overcome teaching difficulties"- (FGD02).

Furthermore, Resilient (pseudonym) mentioned that he was actively engaged in faculty meetings and professional learning communities, leveraging these platforms to collaborate with colleagues, discuss shared concerns, and collectively seek assistance. By participating in these collaborative spaces, he fostered a sense of teamwork and cooperation among his peers, enabling them to work together towards common goals, share insights, and support each other in their professional development journey.

"I actively participated in faculty meetings and professional learning communities. These platforms allowed me to collaborate with colleagues, share concerns, and seek assistance collectively"- (FGD04).

Asking Students Feedback

Neophyte instructors at a local college understand the value of asking students for feedback about their experiences in the classroom. By seeking input directly from their students, these new instructors gain valuable insights into the effectiveness of their teaching methods, the clarity of their instructions, and the overall learning experience. This feedback loop allows them to make necessary adjustments, address any concerns, and continuously improve their teaching practices to better meet the needs of their students. It also fosters a sense of collaboration and communication between instructors and students, creating a more engaging and supportive learning environment.

Libra (pseudonym) mentioned that she believes in being flexible and engaging students through a variety of teaching techniques, always seeking feedback to make sure she's meeting the diverse learning needs of her students. This approach allows her to adapt her teaching style and methods to suit different students' preferences and abilities, fostering a positive and effective learning environment for everyone.

"I embrace flexibility, encourage student engagement through various instructional methods, and continuously seek feedback to ensure that I am meeting the diverse learning needs of my students"- (IDI07).

Moreover, Supportive (pseudonym) mentioned that she often communicated with her students to grasp their unique learning preferences and needs, which empowered her to adjust her teaching methods accordingly and offer personalized assistance whenever necessary. This approach enabled her to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, ensuring that each student had the opportunity to thrive and succeed based on their individual strengths and challenges.

"I regularly communicated with students to understand their learning preferences and needs. This allowed me to adapt my teaching approaches and provide personalized support where necessary" – (FGD02).

Furthermore, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) mentioned that she actively sought feedback from her students, valuing their input and perspectives to gain a deeper understanding of their learning needs. This approach allowed her to identify areas for improvement in her teaching methods and make necessary adjustments to better support her students' learning experiences. By incorporating student feedback, she aimed to create a more effective and engaging learning environment tailored to the unique needs of her students.

"I actively sought feedback from students themselves. Their input and perspectives helped me understand their learning needs better and find ways to improve my teaching methods"- (FGD05).

In addition to that, Versatile (pseudonym) mentioned that she emphasized student involvement and autonomy in the learning journey by providing opportunities for student voice and choice. This was achieved through offering various options for assignments and projects, allowing students to demonstrate their understanding in ways that aligned with their strengths, abilities, and personal interests. By incorporating this approach, she aimed to enhance student engagement, motivation, and ownership of their learning experiences.

"I encouraged student voice and choice in the learning process. By offering options for assignments and projects, students could showcase their understanding in ways that suited their abilities and interests"- (FGD07).

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights they can share to other neophyte instructors and to the academe in general?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants, respectively, hence, several sub- questions were asked. The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, three major themes emerged: Widen and Explore More Professional Growth Opportunities, Need for More Professional and Technical Support, and Consider Giving Mentorship Programs.

Table 4. *Emerging Themes and Supporting Statements on the Insights of Neophyte Instructors in a Local College*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Widen and Explore More Professional Growth Opportunities	<p>"Well, I believe one of those, which I bet is very important, is to further your studies, your studies rather. For example, after you at one point, you proceed with Masters or Doctorate in the future. Because in studying, for example, I am talking about formal education, it could really give you not only additional qualification but also learning. You learn and at the same time you meet people that you could learn from. You could expand your network, your connection. You could also, of course, enrich your knowledge about a certain subject, especially if you want to master a certain field. You always need to be equipped with new education, new insights, because learning is endless. So as a teacher, it is also important that we really embody the essence of lifelong learning...Maybe one thing that I could suggest is to give the Neophyte instructors, especially in college, the chance to further their studies because I believe it is a win-win situation"- (IDI01).</p> <p>"Participate any events because it will really help you in terms of professional growth"- (IDI03).</p> <p>"The resources or opportunities that I would suggest to new instructors to continue their learning is the encouragement to become successful one day and may able to build future through endurance"- (IDI06)</p> <p>"Engaging in action research or participating in research projects can contribute to ongoing development. Collaborating with colleagues on research initiatives allows for deeper exploration of teaching practices and pedagogical approaches"- (FGD06)</p> <p>"New instructors should consider joining professional learning communities or networks focused on teaching and</p>

Need for More Professional and Technical Support

learning. These communities provide opportunities for collaboration, resource sharing, and ongoing professional growth”- (FGD07).

“As a neophyte instructor I can say that allocating a conducive faculty office in order that can help us, neophyte instructors”-(IDI02).

“As a teacher, my suggestions to the administration to address the needs of neophyte instructors would include offering comprehensive orientation programs that cover both theoretical and practical aspects of teaching, as well as in Institutions could consider implementing incentives or recognition programs that acknowledge and reward the hard work and dedication of neophyte instructors. By supporting these educators, institutions can ensure a positive and successful transition into their teaching careers”-(IDI06).

“Regular check-ins and support systems should be established to ensure that new instructors have access to resources, feedback, and opportunities for professional development”-(FGD03).

“It would be beneficial for the administration to establish a comprehensive on boarding program for new instructors. This program could include orientation sessions, mentorship opportunities, and ongoing support”-(FGD05)

“The administration should provide opportunities for new instructors to participate in curriculum development and decision-making processes. Involving them in these discussions can contribute to their growth and create a sense of ownership”-(FGD06).

Consider Giving Mentorship Programs

“To address the needs of neophyte instructors, I recommend that the administration provide mentorship programs, establish regular opportunities for collaboration and sharing of best practices, and offer targeted professional development sessions focused on the specific challenges faced by new instructors”-(IDI04).

“The academe should provide to the neophyte instructors a student counselling, teacher training, and the use of technology and parent-teacher communication...”- (IDI05)

“Institutions could provide resources such as online platforms or discussion groups where educators can ask questions, seek advice, and engage in meaningful conversations about effective teaching strategies. By strengthening support systems, local colleges can improve retention rates among new educators and create a more positive and productive learning environment for both students and teachers alike” – (IDI06).

“As a teacher, my insights to enhance support systems for new educators in a local college would involve fostering a culture of collaboration and mentorship among faculty members. This could be achieved by encouraging experienced teachers to share their expertise and provide guidance to newer educators, implementing formal mentorship programs, and creating opportunities for peer learning and knowledge sharing”- (IDI07).

“The academe should establish formal mentorship programs where new instructors can be paired with experienced educators. This mentorship can provide guidance, support, and a platform for sharing experiences”-(FGD01).

Widen and Explore More Professional Growth Opportunities

Neophyte instructors at a local college are actively seeking to widen and explore more professional growth opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and career development. They are eager to participate in workshops, conferences, and professional development programs that offer new teaching strategies and insights.

Aries (pseudonym) mentioned that she believes that one of the most important things for teachers is to continue their education, such as pursuing a Master's or Doctorate in the future. Formal education not only provides additional qualifications but also enriches knowledge, offers learning opportunities, and helps expand one's professional network. By furthering their studies, teachers can master specific fields, gain new insights, and embody the principle of lifelong learning. She suggests that giving new college instructors the opportunity to further their studies would be beneficial for both the instructors and the educational institutions, making it a win-win situation.

“Additional qualification but also learning. You learn and at the same time you meet people that you could learn from... So as a teacher, it's also important that we really embody the essence of lifelong learning... Maybe one thing that I could suggest is to give the Neophyte instructors, especially in college, the chance to further their studies because I believe it's a win-win situation”-(IDI01).

In addition, Gemini (pseudonym) mentioned that she encourages participation in events because it significantly contributes to professional growth. By engaging in various events, individuals can gain new knowledge, expand their skills, and network with other professionals, all of which are crucial for advancing in their careers.

“Participate any events because it will really help you in terms of professional growth”- (IDI03).

Moreover, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that he suggests that new instructors should seek out resources and opportunities that encourage them to keep learning and growing. He believes that with persistence and endurance, these new instructors can achieve success and build a bright future. By continuously developing their skills and knowledge, they will be better equipped to thrive in their teaching careers.

“The resources or opportunities that I would suggest to new instructors to continue their learning is the encouragement to become successful one day and may able to build future through endurance”- (IDI06).

Besides, Reflective (pseudonym) mentioned that engaging in action research or participating in research projects contributes to ongoing development. By collaborating with colleagues on these research initiatives, teachers can deeply explore and refine their teaching

practices and pedagogical approaches. This collaborative effort not only enhances their own skills but also promotes a continuous improvement culture within their educational community.

“Engaging in action research or participating in research projects can contribute to ongoing development. Collaborating with colleagues on research initiatives allows for deeper exploration of teaching practices and pedagogical approaches”- (FGD06).

Furthermore, Versatile (pseudonym) mentioned that new instructors are encouraged to join professional learning communities or networks that focus on teaching and learning. These groups offer valuable opportunities for collaboration with other educators, sharing resources, and continuous professional development. By participating in these communities, new teachers can enhance their skills, gain new insights, and stay updated with the latest educational practices.

“New instructors should consider joining professional learning communities or networks focused on teaching and learning. These communities provide opportunities for collaboration, resource sharing, and ongoing professional growth”- (FGD07).

Need for More Professional and Technical Support

Neophyte instructors at a local college often find themselves in need of more professional and technical support to navigate the complexities of their new roles. These early-career educators face challenges in curriculum development, classroom management, and integrating technology into their teaching. Without sufficient mentorship, professional development opportunities, and technical resources, they struggle to meet the demands of both administrative responsibilities and effective teaching. Enhanced support systems, such as regular training sessions, access to experienced mentors, and reliable technical assistance, are crucial for helping these instructors build confidence, develop their skills, and succeed in fostering a productive learning environment for their students.

Taurus (pseudonym) mentioned that as a new instructor, he believes that having a well-equipped and supportive faculty office is crucial for helping novice instructors like himself. This kind of environment can provide the necessary resources and support to thrive in their roles.

“As a neophyte instructor I can say that allocating a conducive faculty office in order that can help us, neophyte instructors”- (IDI02).

In addition, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that his recommendations to the administration to support novice instructors would involve suggesting comprehensive orientation programs that encompass both theoretical knowledge and practical teaching skills. Additionally, he would propose the implementation of incentives or recognition programs within institutions to acknowledge and reward the efforts and commitment of new instructors. By providing this support and recognition, institutions can facilitate a smoother and more successful transition for these educators into their teaching careers, ultimately contributing to a positive and nurturing teaching environment.

“As a teacher, my suggestions to the administration to address the needs of neophyte instructors would include offering comprehensive orientation programs that cover both theoretical and practical aspects of teaching, as well as in Institutions could consider implementing incentives or recognition programs that acknowledge and reward the hard work and dedication of neophyte instructors. By supporting these educators, institutions can ensure a positive and successful transition into their teaching careers”- (IDI06).

Moreover, Patient (pseudonym) mentioned that it’s important to set up regular check-ins and support systems for new instructors so they can have the resources, feedback, and chances for professional growth they need. This kind of structure ensures that they feel supported and can improve their teaching skills effectively.

“Regular check-ins and support systems should be established to ensure that new instructors have access to resources, feedback, and opportunities for professional development”- (FGD03).

In addition, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) mentioned that establishing a comprehensive on boarding program for new instructors would be advantageous for the administration. Such a program could encompass orientation sessions to familiarize new instructors with the school's policies, procedures, and culture, mentorship opportunities to provide guidance and support from experienced educators, and ongoing support mechanisms to address any challenges or questions that arise during the initial period. This structured approach to on boarding can help new instructors feel more confident and prepared in their roles, leading to improved job satisfaction and performance.

“A comprehensive on boarding program for new instructors. This program could include orientation sessions, mentorship opportunities, and ongoing support”- (FGD05).

Furthermore, Reflective (pseudonym) mentioned that the administration ought to offer chances for new instructors to engage in curriculum development and decision-making procedures. By including them in these conversations, it can support their professional development and foster a sense of ownership over their work. This involvement not only helps them grow but also enhances their commitment and investment in the institution's goals and objectives.

“It would be beneficial for the administration to establish the administration should provide opportunities for new instructors to participate in curriculum development and decision-making processes. Involving them in these discussions can contribute to their growth and creat a sense of ownership”- (FGD06).

Consider Giving Mentorship Programs

Neophyte instructors at a local college could greatly benefit from mentorship programs. These programs could pair them with experienced faculty members who can provide guidance, support, and practical advice as they navigate their roles. Mentorship can offer valuable insights into effective teaching strategies, classroom management techniques, and ways to integrate technology into lessons. Additionally, mentors can help new instructors build confidence, develop their professional skills, and navigate the challenges of academia. By establishing mentorship programs, the college can create a supportive environment that fosters growth, learning, and success for neophyte instructors as they embark on their teaching careers.

Cancer (pseudonym) mentioned that to support new teachers, she suggests that the administration implement mentorship programs, create regular chances for collaboration and sharing of effective teaching strategies, and conduct targeted professional development sessions tailored to the unique challenges new instructors encounter. These initiatives can greatly benefit novice educators by providing them with guidance, networking opportunities, and skills development to navigate their roles more effectively and enhance their teaching abilities.

“To address the needs of neophyte instructors, I recommend that the administration provide mentorship programs, establish regular opportunities for collaboration and sharing of best practices, and offer targeted professional development sessions focused on the specific challenges faced by new instructors”-(IDI04).

On the other hand, Leo (pseudonym) mentioned that she believes that the academic sector should offer new teachers support in the form of student counselling, teacher training programs, access to technology, and facilitate effective communication between parents and teachers. These resources are crucial for novice instructors as they navigate their roles in education. Counselling can help them address student needs and behavioral issues, while training programs enhance their teaching skills and techniques. Access to technology allows for innovative and engaging lessons, while strong communication between teachers and parents fosters a collaborative learning environment that benefits students' overall academic and personal development.

“The academe should provide to the neophyte instructors a student counselling, teacher training, and the use of technology and parent-teacher communication...”- (IDI05).

Additionally, Virgo (pseudonym) mentioned that one suggestion is for institutions to offer resources like online platforms or discussion groups where educators can interact, ask questions, share advice, and have meaningful discussions about effective teaching methods. By enhancing these support systems, local colleges can boost retention rates among new teachers and foster a positive and productive learning environment for both students and educators. This kind of collaborative approach can lead to continuous professional growth and better outcomes for everyone involved in the education process.

“Institutions could provide resources such as online platforms or discussion groups where educators can ask questions, seek advice, and engage in meaningful conversations about effective teaching strategies. By strengthening support systems, local colleges can improve retention rates among new educators and create a more positive and productive learning environment for both students and teachers alike” – (IDI06).

Moreover, Libra (pseudonym) mentioned that she believes that to improve support systems for new educators in a local college, fostering a culture of collaboration and mentorship among faculty members is crucial. Her approach involves encouraging experienced teachers to share their knowledge and offer guidance to newer educators, establishing formal mentorship programs, and creating platforms for peer learning and knowledge exchange. By promoting collaboration and mentorship, she aims to create a supportive environment that helps new educators thrive and grow professionally.

“As a teacher, my insights to enhance support systems for new educators in a local college would involve fostering a culture of collaboration and mentorship among faculty members. This could be achieved by encouraging experienced teachers to share their expertise and provide guidance to newer educators, implementing formal mentorship programs, and creating opportunities for peer learning and knowledge sharing”-(IDI07).

Furthermore, Adaptable (pseudonym) mentioned that the academic sector ought to create structured mentorship initiatives, pairing new teachers with seasoned educators. She believes that such mentorship programs can offer valuable guidance, support, and a platform for exchanging experiences. This setup can be instrumental in helping new instructors navigate the challenges of teaching, gain insights from experienced mentors, and build a strong foundation for their professional growth.

“The academe should establish formal mentorship programs where new instructors can be paired with experienced educators. This mentorship can provide guidance, support, and a platform for sharing experiences”-(FGD01).

Conclusions

The study delves into the experiences of neophyte instructors at a local college in preparing and producing articles for student publication. This exploration holds particular significance for the college, as it offers valuable insights into how new instructors navigate challenges and develop strategies for success in this aspect of their professional roles. By understanding the experiences of

neophyte instructors, the college can identify safe and effective measures to support them in coping with challenges. This insight can lead to the creation of concrete solutions that promote continuous learning and development among new instructors as they contribute to student publications. Ultimately, these findings aim to serve as a practical guide for future neophyte instructors facing similar experiences in the college setting.

Neophyte instructors in a local college encountered various challenges as they entered the teaching profession. Exploring aspects such as emotional intelligence, adapting to diverse lifestyles, managing physical demands, and learning coping strategies from interactions with others, they underwent significant self-discovery and personal growth. Additionally, it's imperative for the college to provide support for their mental well-being, given the potential stressors new instructors face, such as managing public expectations and conducting interviews with students or colleagues. This support can help them navigate the complexities of teaching and maintain their overall well-being while transitioning into their roles as educators.

Furthermore, the experiences of neophyte instructors in a local college can also greatly benefit from this research project. To prepare for interviews, they should focus on creating a positive atmosphere and practicing open communication with their colleagues. Neophyte instructors can benefit from receiving constructive criticism on specific issues, allowing them to express their opinions and gain a voice within the academic community. This collaborative approach fosters a supportive environment for new instructors to grow and improve in their teaching practices.

Implication for Further Research

The in-depth interviews and focus group discussions shed light on the experiences of neophyte instructors in a local college. These discussions provided valuable insights into the challenges they faced and the experiences they encountered during their early teaching careers. Further research should aim to recognize and delve deeper into these experiences to gain a comprehensive understanding of the journey and development of new instructors in the academic setting.

The experiences of neophyte instructors in a local college highlighted their appreciation for the developmental opportunities they encountered while transitioning into their roles. As they navigated the challenges of teaching, they gained a deeper understanding of themselves and honed their ability to handle various responsibilities. These experiences can serve as a foundation for future research focusing on exploring the emotional aspects of teaching and mentoring.

Additionally, this study specifically focused on the experiences of neophyte Instructors within a local college setting. Given this limitation, future research endeavours could broaden their scope to include insights from new educators in various college institutions or universities. By doing so, researchers can compare and contrast the challenges faced by neophyte instructors across different academic settings, thereby gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse coping strategies employed in the early stages of teaching careers

The experiences of neophyte instructors in a local college highlight their belief in taking responsible actions as educators. They emphasize the importance of continuous improvement through practical application in the classroom. According to them, possessing the necessary skills and knowledge as a new instructor is fundamental to enhancing the classroom environment and fostering effective teaching practices.

The experiences of neophyte instructors in a local college revealed various coping strategies they utilized to navigate their roles effectively. These strategies included Adjusting and Adapting Teaching Strategies, Seeking Assistance and Support from Colleagues, Reflecting and Self-Assessing for Improvement, Having Work-Life Balance, Participating on Professional Growth Opportunities, and Asking Students Feedback. They expressed motivation stemming from their acceptance of the necessity to cope effectively, recognizing challenges as opportunities for learning rather than setbacks. This mind-set enabled them to approach their roles with resilience and a proactive attitude towards professional development.

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